

ION-ACTIVITY MEASUREMENT WITH RESIN-MEMBRANE ELECTRODES: MEASUREMENT OF ZINC, CADMIUM AND MANGANESE ION ACTIVITY IN ELECTROLYTIC SOLUTIONS

By A. S. BASU

Measurement of ion-activity of bivalent metals like Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Mn^{2+} has been made with resin-membrane electrodes, providing values agreeing closely with the theoretical values.

The resin membrane electrodes have been successfully used by Wyllie and Patnode (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 204) and by Sinha for the measurement of ion-activities of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Cu^{2+} (this *Journal*, 1954, **31**, 572; 1955, **32**, 399). The measurements along this line have been extended to other bivalent ions like Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Mn^{2+} , and the results are recorded in this communication.

Mitra and Chatterjee (*ibid.*, 1953, **32**, 751) satisfactorily measured Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Co^{3+} ion-activities in electrolytic solution with clay membrane electrodes.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The resin membranes were prepared according to Sinha (*ibid.*, 1953, **30**, 529) using three commercial cationites, Ionac-C-200, Amberlite-IR-100 and IR-120, by moulding at $120-30^\circ$ at 4000 lbs./P.S.i. pressure with polystyrene as binder. The electrodes were prepared by fixing the membranes, cut into small sizes, to one end of a pyrex tubing with 'Durofix' adhesive. The asymmetry potential was tested as usual. The membranes showing negligible or zero asymmetry potential were then interposed between solutions of known ion-activities. Owing to their stability in solution relative to chlorides, sulphates of zinc, cadmium and manganese were preferred. Such standard solutions were prepared as could make the ratio of ion-activities of any suitable pair equal to 3:1; the activity coefficients were calculated in very dilute as well as in very concentrated solutions by graphical extrapolation (Lewis and Randall, "Thermodynamics"). Mn^{2+} -ion activities were calculated assuming the activity coefficients to be the same as that of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} (Harned and Owen, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions"). The E.M.F. of the following cell:

was measured by means of the L & N K_2 -type potentiometer in combination with a Hartmann and Braun galvanometer having a current density 10^{-10} amps./mm/m. The readings, accurate within ± 0.1 mv, were taken by interchanging the solutions inside and outside the pyrex tubing to check as well as eliminate asymmetry potential, if any.

The equilibrium was attained fairly quickly in concentrated solutions, but in dilute solutions, a longer time, often about 24 hours, was required. The reproducibility of

measurement was checked by repeated changes of solutions. The electrical resistance of the membranes was found to be within one megohm. For comparison, the theoretical E.M.F.s were calculated by means of the simple Nernst equation,

$$E = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a_1}{a_2},$$

which has been proved to hold good in the case of such membrane electrodes as those used here.

TABLE I

Theoretical value = 14.1.

Ratio of activities.		E. M. F.							
Inside.	Outside.	Zn-ion.			Cd-ion.			Mn-ion.	
a_1 .	a_2 .	Ionac-C200.	IRA-100.	IR-120.	Ionac-C200.	IRA-100.	IR-120.	Ionac-C200.	IRA-100.
0.0081	0.0027	14.0	13.8	13.7	11.9	13.9	11.6	13.6	10.0
		14.2*	13.9*	13.9*	11.5*	13.5*	11.2*	13.0*	10.5*
0.0027	0.0009	14.0	14.0	13.8	13.5	15.0	15.0	13.5	10.5
		13.8*	14.5*	14.5*	13.0*	14.0*	14.0*	14.5*	11.5*
0.0009	0.0003	14.2	13.8	13.0	14.0	15.0	12.5	11.5	11.0
		14.0*	13.0*	12.8*	14.5*	15.5*	13.0*	12.5*	12.5*
0.0003	0.0001	14.0	15.0	16.0	14.6	12.6	11.0	13.5	10.5
		13.5*	15.5*	15.0*	14.0*	11.5*	11.5*	13.0*	10.0*

The first sets of figures correspond to the arrangements of solutions as shown in columns 1 and 2, whereas the second sets, marked with an asterisk, have been obtained by interchanging the solutions inside and outside the membrane electrodes. The mean of the sets is compared with the theoretical values.

Accurate data on the activity coefficients of the salt solutions are not available. Moreover, the Lewis and Randall assumption for the calculation of the activities of ion is very approximate. However, a comparison of the theoretical E.M.F.s with the observed values shows clearly that in spite of the likely discrepancies, mentioned above, the agreement is fairly good. The agreement is more satisfactory within the range ($a=0.0081$ to $a=0.0001$) of solutions. Of the three resins, Ionac-C-200 gives the best performance.

Thanks are due to Dr. S. K. Mukherjee, University College of Science and Technology, for his valuable suggestions and guidance, and to Dr. P. C. Rakshit, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, for his continued interest and for giving laboratory facilities, and also to the Ministry of Education, Govt. of India for the grant of a senior research scholarship.